

Development of Kapok/Polyester Nonwovens for Building Insulation Application

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Abstract:

In this study, needle punched kapok/polyester (PET) blended nonwovens were prepared and characterized for building insulation applications. Nonwovens were manufactured by blending kapok fibres with polyester at three blend ratios (20%, 30%, & 40%). The developed kapok/polyester nonwovens were characterized by thermal insulation applications. Also, the influence of PET blend ratio on the thermal insulation performance of the developed kapok/polyester nonwovens was investigated. There was a reduction in thermal resistance value observed with an increase in polyester percentage in kapok/polyester nonwovens. The performance of kapok/polyester needle punched nonwovens compared with conventional insulation materials. The developed kapok/PET nonwovens had a thermal insulation value on par with that of conventional insulation materials.

Keywords: Kapok, needle punching, nonwoven, polyester, thermal insulation

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the usage of natural fibres such as kenaf, banana, pineapple, bagasse, etc. has increased. These natural fibers are used in the form of short fibres or nonwovens. Because of their excellent balanced properties and biodegradable nature, there is lots of research going on in the technical textiles area. Kapok is a silky fiber that encloses the seeds of kapok trees (*Ceibapentandra*), and the color is yellowish or light-brown with a silk-like lustre. In contrast to cotton fiber, kapok fiber is made of single-celled plant hairs. It has a hollow lumen (or structure) and a sealed tail with an external radius of 8 ± 3 mm, an internal radius of 7 ± 3 mm, and a length of 20 to 32 mm, which indicates that the lumen makes up 77% of the fiber volume (Figure 1). Kapok fiber has low thermal conductivity and decomposes at a temperature of 296°C . Kapok fiber is comprised of 43% alpha-cellulose, 24% pentosan, 15% lignin, and 6.6% Uronicanhydride. Because of its hollow nature, kapok fiber is commonly used as stuffing material for bedding and pillows. Recently, kapok fiber-based structures have been used for insulation applications. Because of its excellent buoyancy properties, kapok fiber was also used in water safety equipment.

Figure1 - SEM images of kapok fibre (a) longitudinal view (b) cross sectional view

A lot of research has been carried out on kapok fibers for oil absorption and sound insulation applications. But very few studies have been carried out on kapok fibres for thermal insulation applications. Cui, Wang, Wei, and Zhao manufactured wadding by blending kapok fibers with down feather fibers and studied the developed

waddings for cold weather protective clothing. They found that the thermal insulation performance of the developed wadding increased with an increase in the kapok fiber blend percentage [1]. Wang compared the thermal insulation performance of kapok coats and traditional down coats. He found that kapok coats have comparable thermal insulation performance to traditional duckling down coats [2]. Udaya, Karthick, and Gobi manufactured thermal bonded kapok/PP blended nonwoven fabrics and studied the influence of polypropylene blend percentage on the thermal insulation value of kapok/PP blended nonwoven fabrics [3].

Patnaik et al. developed new insulating materials using recycled polyester (rPET) and waste wool fibres for building insulation application. He showed that the developed waste wool/recycled polyester (rPET) nonwovens have good thermal and acoustic insulation properties. The developed nonwovens also had good moisture absorption, flame resistance, and biodegradation behavior [4]. Duran has manufactured needle punched nonwovens from recycled wool and jute fibers. He has studied the thermal insulation properties of the developed nonwovens for building insulation applications [5]. El Wazna et al. manufactured nonwovens using textile waste for building insulation applications. They investigated the influence of nonwoven density and porosity on the thermal insulation performance of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics [6]. Hadded, Benltoufa, and Fayala manufactured needle punched nonwovens from textile fibers waste and studied the thermal insulation performance of the developed nonwovens for building insulation applications [7]. They found that the developed nonwovens have good thermal insulation properties and can be used for the building insulation applications. However, no such work has studied the thermal conductivity behavior of kapok needle punched nonwovens for building insulation applications.

We have manufactured needle punched nonwovens by blending flax fibers with low melt polyester fibers for insulation applications. The effect of needle punching parameters and blend percentage on the insulation properties of the flax/PET nonwovens has been studied [8]. In our previous study, we manufactured needle punched nonwovens by blending pineapple fibers with low melt polyester fibers. The sound and thermal insulation performance of the developed nonwovens have been studied [9]. We are working on natural fibres for their thermal characteristics. Among the natural fibres, kapok fibres have low thermal conductivity and can be used as insulation material in buildings. However, kapok fibers have poor inter-fiber cohesion due to their short length, smooth surface, and low density. Hence, the processing of the kapok by machines is difficult. In this study, polyester fibre was blended with the kapok fibres to improve the process ability. In this study, we have manufactured kapok/PET nonwoven fabrics by needle punching technique for the thermal insulation application. Nonwoven fabrics were manufactured by blending kapok fibres with polyester fibers at three blend ratios (20%, 30%, and 40%). We have studied the effect of blend percentage of polyester on the thermal insulation performance of the developed kapok/ polyester nonwovens.

2. Materials and Methods

Kapok fibers having a length of 26.32 mm and a fineness of 0.71 denier have been sourced in and around Coimbatore, India. Polyester fibers having a length of 38 mm and a fineness of 0.80 denier have been sourced from Reliance Fibers, India.

A. Nonwoven manufacturing

For nonwovens manufacturing, kapok fibers were blended with polyester fibers at three blend ratios (20%, 30% and 40%). The web preparation was done using a laboratory-scale carding machine. Needle punched nonwovens were developed using the needle loom - DI-Loom OUG-II 6. Nonwovens were developed with a punch density of 70 punches/cm² and 10 mm needle penetration depth.

B. Characterization methods

The thickness of the developed nonwovens has been measured under a 2 kPa load using a fabric thickness gauge as per the ASTM D-1777 standard [10]. The kapok/polyester nonwovens have been characterized for areal density, which has been measured as per ASTM D-1910 standard using an electronic balance [11]. The kapok/polyester nonwovens have been characterized for air permeability according to the ASTM D 737 standard using the air permeability tester with a 100 Pa pressure drop [12]. The kapok/polyester nonwovens have been characterized for thermal resistance according to ISO 8301:1991 standards using the heat flow meter apparatus. Five measurements were taken for each test, and the average value was determined.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Physical characteristics of Kapok/Polyester nonwovens

The characteristics of the obtained nonwoven specimens are shown in Table 1. The kapok/ polyester nonwovens had thickness in the range of 7.19–7.73 mm. The random distribution of fibers during nonwoven formation creates this variation in the thickness of the nonwovens. The developed nonwovens had a density in the range of 79.12– 88.63 (Kg/m³). It was noticed that the areal density of the samples decreased when the content of polyester fiber in the nonwoven increased from 20 to 40%.

Table 1 – Characteristics of Kapok/Polyester Nonwovens

Sample	GSM	Thickness (mm)	Density (Kg/m ³)	Air permeability (cm ³ /cm ² /s)	Thermal conductivity (W/ mK)	Thermal resistance (m ² K/W)
80/20 (Kapok/PET)	419.22	4.73	88.63	57.6	0.0166	0.446
70/30 (Kapok/PET)	373.22	4.40	84.83	62.2	0.0213	0.388
60/40 (Kapok/PET)	331.52	4.19	79.12	87.2	0.0221	0.350

The effect of polyester blend percentage on the air permeability of the developed kapok/ polyester nonwovens is shown in Figure 2. With the increase in polyester blend percentage in kapok/polyester nonwovens, an increase in air permeability value was observed. This may be due to a decrease in thickness and basis weight with an increase in PET %. It was noticed that the variable in the regression equation has a positive co-efficient value, which confirms that the increase in polyester blend percentage increases the air permeability value of the kapok/ polyester nonwovens. The linear regression curve has a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.914, indicating its goodness of fit.

Figure 2 - Influence of polyester blend % on air permeability of kapok/polyester nonwovens

3.2 Thermal insulation properties of Kapok/Polyester nonwovens

Thermal resistance expresses the ability of the material to prevent heat flow through its thickness over a unit surface area. The influence of polyester blend percentage on the thermal resistance value of the developed kapok/ polyester nonwovens is shown in Figure 3. It was noticed that the thermal resistance value of the kapok/polyester nonwoven decreases with an increase in the polyester blend percentage. In general, polyester fibres have a higher thermal conductivity value compared to kapok fibres. Hence, the increasing polyester blend percentage in the kapok/polyester nonwoven increases the thermal conductivity of the nonwoven and decreases its thermal insulation. It was noticed that the variable in the regression equation has a negative co-efficient value, which confirms the increase in polyester blend percentage decreases the thermal resistance. The linear regression curve has a coefficient of determination (R²) value of 0.985, indicating its goodness of fit.

Figure 3 - Influence of polyester blend % on thermal insulation properties of nonwovens

3.3 Comparison of the developed kapok/PET nonwovens with commercial products

Table 2 – Comparison of the manufactured Nonwovens and commercially available insulators

Insulators	Density (Kg/m ³)	Thermal conductivity(W/ mK)	Thermal resistance (m ² K/W)
Kapok/PET nonwovens	79.12– 88.63	0.0166–0.0221	0.350-0.446
Rockwool(rock wool)	40-1200	0.037-0.040	0.27-0.25
Perlite(natural glassy volcanic rock)	32-176	0.04-0.06	0.250-0.166
Vermiculite(natural mineral)	64-130	0.063-0.068	0.158-0.147
Glass wool	24-112	0.032-0.035	0.312-0.285
Expanded polystyrene	16-35	0.037-0.038	0.270-0.263
Extruded polystyrene	26-45	0.030-0.0320	0.330-0.312
Polyurethane foam	30-80	0.02-0.027	0.50-0.37

The performance of the kapok/ polyester needle punched nonwovens has been compared with commercially available building insulation products and is given in Table 2. The developed kapok/polyester nonwovens have a thermal conductivity in the range of 0.0166–0.0221 W/mK, which is lower than that of the commercially available insulation materials. The developed kapok/polyester nonwovens have better thermal insulation values compared to commercially available insulating materials. Also, the nonwovens developed in this study are eco-friendly, and their production does not contribute to environmental pollution.

4. Conclusion

For insulation applications, nonwovens materials are ideal because of their porous structure and unique fibre orientation. In this study, nonwovens were manufactured by blending kapok fibers with polyester for building insulation applications. The nonwovens developed with a higher polyester blend percentage showed a higher air permeability value. The nonwovens developed with higher polyester blend percentage showed a lower thermal insulation value. The developed nonwovens have a thermal insulation value in the range of 0.350-0.446 (m²K/W), which is better than that of commercially available products. The kapok/polyester nonwovens developed in this study are low-cost and environmentally friendly and can be used for building insulation applications.

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